

SELF-HEALING OF SKIN-STIFFENER DEBOND SPECIMENS UNDER FATIGUE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Intralaminar damage is one of the first damage mechanisms to occur in fibre reinforced polymers. Even though the effect on the mechanical properties is limited, it acts as an initiation point for subsequent interlaminar damage. Within this study, a vascular self-healing approach has been used in cross-ply laminates in order to mitigate transverse intralaminar damage by infusing low viscosity epoxy resins into the damage plane. Under static loading, the stiffness was recovered successfully, however, under fatigue loading the mechanical properties of the healing agent proved to be insufficient. The vascular healing approach was also applied to skin-stiffener debond specimens loaded under tensile-tensile fatigue. In this case the skin failed by material failure of the off-axis plies leading to intralaminar matrix damage. By introducing the vascular network it was possible to infuse the damage sites and partly recover the structural stiffness, however, the location of the vasculature was shown to be detrimental to the mechanical properties of the structure under fatigue loading. Ongoing work is underway to optimise both the healing agent performance and vasculature location for the components described above.

1 INTRODUCTION

Locally stiffened or ‘stringer-skin’ structures are extensively used for lightweight, high performance applications (e.g. aerospace). This design philosophy is efficient, as the skin takes the in-plane loads, while the stiffening elements provide increased bending stiffness and a reduction in the effective buckling length. A variety of failure modes exist, such as material failure of the skin or stiffener material, buckling and skin-stiffener separation [1].

The current principal design philosophy employed in the aerospace sector for fibre reinforced polymers (FRPs) implements a “no damage growth” approach [2]. In addition, the failure sequence of skin-stiffened structures are designed to be damage tolerant in order that benign failure mechanisms, such as stiffener crippling [1], occur first and buckling is not acceptable below design ultimate load [3]. This limits the potential weight savings offered in the structural application of FRPs. The current design philosophy incurs additional time-consuming, non-destructive inspections. Detection of a damage event can lead to unscheduled downtime of the aircraft in order for repairs to be carried out.

One possibility to achieve more lightweight designs is to reduce conservative safety factors in aircraft or other safety critical structures, and to implement a bio-inspired approach where the structure has the ability to sense the health state (Structural Health Monitoring - SHM) [4] and react upon a damage event (self-healing) [5]. Whereas the former is already being considered by the original equipment manufacturers, the latter is still in its infancy.

Two different approaches exist for self-healing [5]: (1) an intrinsic approach, which relies on a host polymer matrix to exhibit reversible polymerisation [6]; and (2) an extrinsic approach, in which an additional liquid healing agent is introduced into the crack plane. This healing agent may be either embedded in microcapsules [7] or hollow glass fibres [8-9] in the matrix material or pumped through a vascular network [10-11], which is generally manufactured using a lost wax approach [12]. Upon a damage event, the healing agent will flow into the crack plane, polymerise and bridge the fractured crack planes in order to restore mechanical performance. This vascular network approach has the greatest

benefit in that larger damage volumes can be infused, and that the channels can also be used as detectors for SHM [13].

To date, the main focus of research into self-healing for FRPs has been focused on the recovery of mechanical properties after delamination damage. This has been studied under compression after impact (CAI), Mode I and Mode II. Despite the fact that fibre debonding and intralaminar damage are the main damage initiation mechanisms in FRPs [14], there are few examples to be found in the literature [15–17] which address this damage mode via self-healing solutions. Also, a limited number of publications can be found where more complex loading cases, with a variety of damage modes, are being addressed simultaneously by self-healing [18–21].

The aim of this research is twofold: First, intralaminar damage arising under tensile loading in cross-ply [22] laminates is addressed both under static and fatigue loading. In a second phase, the potential for application of a self-healing solution within a skin-stiffened structure, which suffers from material failure in the skin, is explored. The selected healing approach is an embedded vascular network.

Testing of skin-stiffened structures, however, is both labour and time intensive. Therefore, testing is carried out on simplified skin-stiffener debond specimens [23] which mimic the stress state at the tip of the flange.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Cross-ply laminates

Figure 1 shows the cross-ply specimen geometry. Specimens were manufactured using a pre-impregnated E-glass/913 epoxy (Hexcel, UK) using the manufacturer’s recommended curing cycle (60 min at 125°C and 700 kN/mm², heating rate 2-8°C/min). The panels were manufactured by hand lay-up with a [0₄,90₄]_S lay-up. Glass fibre end tabs were bonded to the laminate prior to cutting the specimens to size.

The plies containing vasculae had minimal fibrous sections removed and stainless steel wires (diameter 0.56mm), coated with a release agent, were placed between these cut-outs according to the manufacturing method proposed by *Norris et al.* [24]. The vasculae were placed in the 0₂/90₂ plies running along the length of the specimens in order to address transverse matrix damage (refer to Figure 1).

Figure 1: Specimen dimensions and vasculae location for (i) cross ply and (ii) skin-stiffener debond specimens.

2.2 Skin-Stiffener debond specimen

The geometry of the specimens is shown in Figure 1. Both the skin and flange were manufactured using a pre-impregnated E-glass/913 epoxy (Hexcel, UK) using the manufacturer's recommended curing cycle (60 min at 125°C and 700kN/mm², heating rate 2-8°C/min). The panels were manufactured by hand lay-up. The pre-cured flange [-45₂/0₂/45₂/90₂]_S was cut to size and the edges chamfered to 20°. The skin [45₂/90₂/-45₂/0₂]_S was laid up, assembled with the flange and cured. Prior to cutting the specimens to size, glass fibre end tabs were bonded.

Vasculcs were manufactured in a similar way as for the cross-ply laminates and placed in the 90₂/-45₂ plies, as shown in Figure 1.

2.3 Test Method

A Schenck Hydropuls® PSA universal testing machine, equipped with a calibrated load cell of 100 kN range, was used for static and fatigue tests.

Static and fatigue healing tests were performed for the cross-ply laminates. For the static healing tests, specimens were loaded to 15kN (340 MPa, corresponding to 75% of the failure stress) and then unloaded under displacement control at a rate of 2mm/min. The stiffness was determined using the strain obtained via video extensometry (Imetrum) during the loading and unloading cycle.

The healing performance for the static tests is defined as follows:

$$\eta_{static,E} = \frac{E_{healed} - E_{damaged}}{E_{pristine} - E_{damaged}} \quad (1)$$

$E_{pristine}$ corresponds to the modulus during the first loading cycle, $E_{damaged}$ the modulus during the first unloading cycle and E_{healed} the modulus during the loading cycle after the healing event.

During the fatigue test, the stiffness was determined from the load displacement data of the test machine. The damage accumulation and healing performance was assessed in terms of stiffness loss as a function of cycles.

The skin-stiffener debond specimens were tested under fatigue testing under load control ($F_{max}=10$ kN, $R=0.1$) corresponding to approximately 40% of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS). During fatigue testing, the stiffness was determined from the load displacement data of the test machine. Specimens without vasculcs were cycled for 40 000 cycles. Some tests were interrupted in order to assess the damage state by optical microscopy. The vascularised specimens were tested for 5 000 cycles, after which the healing agent was injected. Following curing of the healing resin, the specimens were re-tested as described above.

2.4 Healing protocol

The commercially available low viscosity epoxy resin RT151 (Resintech) and epoxy blends, as described in [17], have been used in this study. The constituents of this resin are Epon 828 (Polysciences), – an oligomeric diglycidylether bisphenol A (DGEBA); a reactive epoxy diluent, polypropylene diglycidylether (PPGE); a toughening agent, HyPox RA840 and an amine curing agent, diethylentriamine (DETA). HyPox RA840 is a DGEBA based resin system with a carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile (CTBN) adduct on 19% of the epoxy monomers. Upon reaction, the CTBN is displaced from the epoxy monomer and precipitates into particles which toughen the system [17].

	RT151	Epon 828	HyPox RA840	PPGE
RT151	100%	-	-	-
20B	-	80%	-	20%
30B	-	70%	-	30%
30B_R	-	50%	20%	30%
50B_R	-	30%	20%	50%

Table 1. Healing agents used in this study

Figure 2: (i) Optical micrograph with damage highlighted with UV dye penetrant and (ii) SEM of transverse damage.

The edges of the specimens were sealed with an adhesive release tape prior to infusing the healing agent into the specimens using a Nexus syringe pump. The curing schedule of 1h at 65°C was applied for the RT151 resin and 1h at 45°C and 3 days at room temperature for the other blends [17]. Afterwards, the specimens were reloaded under either static or fatigue loading.

3 TEST RESULTS FROM INTRALAMINAR DAMAGE HEALING

Error! Reference source not found. shows the intralaminar damage pattern observed both under tensile static and fatigue loading. Each transverse damage site developed instantaneously across the complete width of the specimen, at a certain load level or a certain amount of cycles. At the tip of the transverse damage, delaminations were seen to initiate and propagate along the 0° / 90° interface [25]. When unloaded, the transverse damage width is approximately 8 μm and meanders through the 90° fibres. However, from the micrograph it is apparent that there is continuous damage, which is located normal to the vasculature orientation. A healing agent injected into the vasculature should flow into the damage if the viscosity of the healing agent is low and sufficient pressure is applied. In a first attempt designed to prove the ability to infuse the damage plane, a red dye penetrant was successfully injected [17].

3.1 Static tests

Figure 3 (i) shows a representative stress-strain plot for specimens loaded to 15kN before healing and after healing. Figure 3 (ii) provides a summary of the resultant healing efficiency values.

For all tested healing agents, the initial modulus was restored successfully. The highest efficiency was achieved for RT151 with a value of 153%, whereas the lowest was achieved for the 30B_R healing

Figure 3: (i) A representative stress –strain graph for a specimen before and after healing and (ii) healing efficiencies for different healing agents.

Figure 4: Stiffness decay as a function of cycles before and after healing. Note: A trendline for pristine reference specimens has been added.

resin (30B_R – 114%). The latter was also the healing agent with the highest viscosity and it is assumed that some of the smallest regions of the transverse damage might not have been fully infused. This may also be the reason for the important scatter observed in the healing efficiencies.

For the pristine loading, the stiffness decays at around 230 MPa with the initiation and propagation of transverse damage. However, for the healed specimens, this decay starts at around 130 to 160 MPa and the highest values have been observed for the healing resins RT151 and 30B_R.

3.2 Fatigue tests

Figure 4 shows the mean values of the stiffness decay as a function of cycles prior to healing and after healing for the three healing agents (RT151, 20B and 30B_R). It has to be noted that the stiffness decays rapidly after the healing event. For the 20B healing agent, no recovery effect was observed. The highest recovery was observed for 30B_R. This may be due to the toughening agent, which inhibits fast crack propagation from the incompletely healed regions, which act as stress concentrations for further loading.

4 DAMAGE RECOVERY IN SKIN STIFFENER DEBOND SPECIMENS

4.1. Damage pattern identification

Figure 5 shows the stiffness decay and the observed damage pattern as a function of cycles. Two different damage propagation regimes can be observed. Up to approximately 7 500 cycles a steep stiffness decay was observed and the damage pattern was transverse damage in the central off-axis plies. Due to the decrement of the skin stiffness, the localised stiffening effect of the flange increased, leading to larger through thickness stresses at the tip of the flange. At around 10 000 cycles, a delamination initiated at the resin pocket located at the tip of the flange and this delamination propagated further along the skin-flange interface and had a tendency to migrate into the 90₂/45₂ interface due to the resolved tensile stresses [26]. It can, therefore, be stated that two damage mechanisms are present: (1) the transverse damage in the skin and (2) the delamination initiating at the tip of the flange and propagating either along the skin/flange interface or the 45₂/90₂ interface.

Figure 5: Stiffness decay as a function of cycles and representative observed damage pattern.

The location of the vasculae as shown in Figure 1 was selected in order to be able to address both the intralaminar damage in the skin and the delamination initiating at the tip of the flange.

2.1. Self healing

The introduction of embedded vasculae into the specimen had a negative effect on the mechanical performance of the specimen. For the baseline specimen, after 5 000 cycles a mean stiffness reduction of approximately 6% was observed, whereas for the vascularised specimen this reduction was twice as large. This was attributed to a larger damage footprint. For the baseline specimen only transverse damage was observed (Figure 5), however, in the case of vascularised specimens additional tip delaminations were observed (Figure 6 (i)). It is assumed that the localised stress concentration caused by the vasculae promotes the delamination initiation and progression in the resin pocket at the flange tip.

Figure 6 (ii) shows the stiffness recovery as a function of cycles. Prior to fatigue testing, the specimens were loaded to maximum fatigue loading (10 kN) and for the specimens healed with RT151 the transverse damage reopened. Therefore, no recovery can be observed with this healing agent. In contrast, for the specimens healed with 30B_R, the damage only partly re opened and some limited stiffness recovery was observed under fatigue loading.

Figure 6: (i) Fractography showing the damage after 5 000 cycles for a specimen with vasculures (Measuring bar corresponds to 2mm) and (ii) stiffness decay as a function of cycles, prior to and after healing using two different healing agents.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Within this study the potential to address intralaminar matrix damage with a vascular network in FRPs is addressed. A healing agent infused into a vasculature oriented normal to the matrix damage is capable of wetting out the damage, and able to fully recover the stiffness after a static damage event. It has to be noted that the mechanical properties of the healing agents studied degrade rapidly during fatigue testing and, therefore, research to develop suitable healing agents that combine low viscosity for infusion, compatibility with the host matrix and mechanical properties in terms of strength and toughness is in progress, with the aim of demonstrating more effective healing under fatigue conditions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Kassapoglou. Design and Analysis of Composite Structures with applications to Aerospace Structures, in *Design and Analysis of Composite Structures with applications to Aerospace Structures*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2013, pp. 223–258.
- [2] X. Chen, H. Ren, C. Bil, and J. Cai. Repair Tolerance Analysis for Composite Structures Using Probabilistic Methodologies, *Journal of Aircraft*, vol. 51, no. 6, 2014, (doi: 10.2514/1.C032635).

- [3] D. Jegley. Structural Efficiency of Stitched Composite Panels with Stiffener Crippling, *Journal of Aircraft*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 1273–1280, 2005, (doi: 10.2514/1.11845).
- [4] C. Boller. Ways and options for aircraft structural health management, *Smart materials and structures*, vol. 10, pp. 432–440, 2001, (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/10/3/302).
- [5] B.J. Blaiszik, S.L.B. Kramer, S.C. Olugebefola, J.S. Moore, N.R. Sottos, and S.R. White. Self-Healing Polymers and Composites, *Annual Review of Materials Research*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 179–211, Jun. 2010, (doi: 10.1146/annurev-matsci-070909-104532).
- [6] J.A. Syrett, C.R. Becer, and D.M. Haddleton. Self-healing and self-mendable polymers, vol. 1, pp. 978–987, 2010, (doi: 10.1039/c0py00104j).
- [7] E. Brown, S. White, and N. Sottos. Retardation and repair of fatigue cracks in a microcapsule toughened epoxy composite – Part I: Manual infiltration, *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 65, no. 15–16, pp. 2466–2473, Dec. 2005, (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.04.020).
- [8] R.S. Trask, and I.P. Bond. Biomimetic self-healing of advanced composite structures using hollow glass fibres, *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 704–710, Jun. 2006, (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/15/3/005).
- [9] J.W.C. Pang, and I.P. Bond. ‘Bleeding composites’—damage detection and self-repair using a biomimetic approach, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 183–188, Feb. 2005, (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.06.016).
- [10] C.J. Norris, J. a P. White, G. McCombe, P. Chatterjee, I.P. Bond, and R.S. Trask. Autonomous stimulus triggered self-healing in smart structural composites, *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 1–10, Sep. 2012, (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/21/9/094027).
- [11] C.J. Norris, G.J. Meadway, M.J. O’Sullivan, I.P. Bond, and R.S. Trask. Self-Healing Fibre Reinforced Composites via a Bioinspired Vasculature, *Advanced Functional Materials*, vol. 21, no. 19, pp. 3624–3633, Oct. 2011, (doi: 10.1002/adfm.201101100).
- [12] R.S. Trask, and I.P. Bond. Bioinspired engineering study of Plantae vasculues for self-healing composite structures., *Journal of the Royal Society, Interface / the Royal Society*, vol. 7, no. 47, pp. 921–931, Jun. 2010, (doi: 10.1098/rsif.2009.0420).
- [13] H. Stehmeier, and H. Speckmann. Comparative Vacuum Monitoring (CVM) Monitoring of fatigue cracking in aircraft structures, in *2nd European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*, Munich, 2004.
- [14] G. Lubineau, and a. Rahaman. A review of strategies for improving the degradation properties of laminated continuous-fiber/epoxy composites with carbon-based nanoreinforcements, *Carbon*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 2377–2395, 2012, (doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2012.01.059).
- [15] A.R. Jones, B.J. Blaiszik, S.R. White, and N.R. Sottos. Full Recovery of Fiber/Matrix Interfacial Bond Strength using a Microencapsulated Solvent-Based Healing System, *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 79, pp. 1–7, Feb. 2013, (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.02.007).
- [16] C. Nielsen, and S. Nemat-Nasser. Crack healing in cross-ply composites observed by dynamic mechanical analysis, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, Nov. 2014, (doi: 10.1016/j.jmps.2014.11.006).
- [17] D.T. Everitt, R. Luterbacher, T.S. Coope, I.P. Bond, R.S. Trask, and D.F. Wass. Optimisation of epoxy blends for use in extrinsic self-healing fibre-reinforced composites, *Polymer*, 2015, (doi: 10.1016/j.quageo.2014.03.002).
- [18] T. Yang, J. Zhang, A.P. Mouritz, and C.H. Wang. Healing of carbon fibre–epoxy composite T-joints using mendable polymer fibre stitching, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 1499–1507, Sep. 2013, (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.08.022).
- [19] T.K. O’Brien, and S.R. White. Assesment of composite delamination self-healing via micro-encapsulation, in *American Society for Proceedings: Composites 23rd Technical Conference*, Memphis, Tennessee, 2008, pp. 116–135.
- [20] S. Minakuchi, D. Sun, and N. Takeda. Hierarchical system for autonomous sensing-healing of delamination in large-scale composite structures, *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 23, no. 11, p. 10, Oct. 2014, (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/23/11/115014).
- [21] J.F. Cullinan, M.R. Wisnom, and I.P. Bond. In-Situ Repair of Composite T-Joints, no. January, pp. 1–10, 2015.
- [22] K.W.K. Garrett, and J.E.J. Bailey. Multiple transverse fracture in 90 cross-ply laminates of a

- glass fibre-reinforced polyester, *Journal of materials science*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 157–168, Jan. 1977, (doi: 10.1007/BF00738481).
- [23] P.J. Minguet, and T.K. O'Brien. Analysis of Test Methods for characterizing skin/stringer debonding failures in reinforced composite panels, in *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Twelfth Volume)*, 1996, pp. 105–124.
- [24] C.J. Norris, I.P. Bond, and R.S. Trask. The role of embedded bioinspired vasculature on damage formation in self-healing carbon fibre reinforced composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 639–648, Jun. 2011, (doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.02.003).
- [25] N. Takeda, and S. Ogihara. Initiation and growth of delamination from the tips of transverse cracks in CFRP cross-ply laminates, *Composites science and technology*, vol. 52, pp. 309–318, 1994, (doi: 10.1016/0266-3538(94)90166-X).
- [26] S. Singh, and E.S. Greenhalgh. Micromechanics of interlaminar fracture in carbon fibre reinforced plastics at multidirectional ply interfaces under static and cyclic loading, *Plastics, rubber and composites processing and applications*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 220–226, 1998.